

COVID-19: Invitation to Introspect and Manifest our Altruism

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For most of us living presently in the world, it is the first time to experience and grapple with a pandemic. I do not know whether we could regard ourselves as blessed or cursed ones to be part of this historical moment! We might have thought in December 2019 that COVID-19 is something to do with Wuhan, China, and perhaps we are pretty safe and never would face it so personally. We might have even read or heard of such pandemics in the remote history caused by brutal killers, example, *cholera* (8 Lakhs death toll in 1910-1911; 1 million from 1852-1860), *bubonic plague* (75-200 million death toll from 1346-1353), *smallpox* (an estimated 300 million people died from smallpox in the 20th century alone), *influenza* (killed 1 million since 1968; 20-50 million between 1918-1920), *HIV/AIDS* (killed more than 36 million people since 1981) etc.

With this terrifying knowledge of pandemic history, it is obvious that one easily succumbs to dread, panic, distress and despair. At the same time, the same pandemic histories also reveal that it is not a time to be merely panicked but to accept it as the author of Ecclesiastes tells that “for everything there is season, and a time for every matter under heaven”. In his words, especially pandemic is “a time to die, a time to weep, a time to mourn, a time to refrain from embracing, a time to lose, a time to keep silence.” (Eccl 3:1-8). In this essay, although there are

many life casualties caused by COVID-19, I would like to approach COVID-19 as an invitation to introspect and manifest our altruism.

Altruism Authenticates Christian Life

Altruism is explained in Oxford dictionary as a principle of considering the welfare and happiness of others before one's own. In other words, it is to be unselfish or other-oriented. George Lobo enumerated four attitudes of the mature Christian conscience, i.e., it should be rational, autonomous, altruistic and responsible. While talking about altruistic attitude of conscience, he says "it is influenced by the needs and interests of one's fellowmen; it is able to sacrifice self-interest for the sake of others"¹.

Jesus gave his life as ransom for others. Therefore, Christian vocation/life is measured by the degree of our altruism, breaking of our self for building the other. But today unfortunately and ironically, we see many in this globalized world leading an individualistic and self-centred life. At this juncture, Coronavirus emphatically tells us to be altruistic to save humanity otherwise the damage and loss of life would be enormous. Let us see some of the meaningful ways in which we are and we could be altruistic at this time of COVID-19 pandemic.

Altruism in Knowing and Sharing Right Information

First of all, we need to get right information regarding coronavirus from a reliable source about its nature, symptoms, precautionary

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measures and treatment. The same we have to share with others. We are bombarded with Himalayan piles of rumours in the social media related to COVID-19. We ought to be altruistic to verify the credibility of the information and then share with others. Unnecessary and unfounded messages we should not pass to others in order to avoid putting them in panic and dread. We could exercise our altruism by sharing the right information to the people who have no access to them, especially the illiterate, children, etc.

Altruism in Personal Quarantining

It has been authoritatively declared that we could avoid the spread of coronavirus if we remain socially distanced from others. We are advised to stay at home and come out only for very necessary purposes, like, to buy provisions, to visit medical doctor or buy medicine, etc. For a modern people who are used to going out and mingling more with friends than family members, it would be really difficult to remain at home quarantined. Even though it's difficult and we dislike, yet by keeping ourselves quarantined and maintaining adequate hygiene (washing of hands and wearing suitable mask) we manifest concretely altruism.

Altruism in Sharing the Resources with the Needy

In this time of pandemic crisis, those who are rich could buy the essential commodities to eat and rest peacefully. But the poor daily labourers and even among them the migrant workers are terribly affected by the implementation of 144 and sudden nationwide lockdown. They have no money to buy food because they have no work. They wanted to be at least united with their family members in their native villages but they have no transport facilities to reach respective places. They are stranded helplessly without shelter and food and many of them died while walking to their places². Of course, the Central and State governments have taken some measures to aid them but

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we not know how much effectively these helps reach them. Altruism demands that at least in our vicinity we do our best to feed the hungry and feel solidarity with people who are stranded in the streets.

Altruism in Prayer

Prayer is a powerful means of expressing our intimate relationship with God as our own “Father” or “Mother” and experiencing God’s Goodness (cf. Mt. 7:11) and Power (cf. Mk. 9: 29). This God is not indifferent to our present suffering, nor pandemic be interpreted primarily as God’s wrath and punishment for our sins. For Catherine LaCugna writes: “The God who does not need nor care for the creature, or who is immune to our suffering, does not exist... The God who keeps a ledger of our sins and failings, the divine policeman, does not exist³.”

We do not pray merely for our own protection from COVID-19 but we pray for the entire humanity with a sense of altruism. We could with firm faith and hope recite the prayer composed beautifully and circulated by Pune Diocese: “O God, in this time of the coronavirus we turn to you in trust and hope. you are ever full of mercy, compassion and love towards us. We ask you, loving Father, to be merciful to us and in your divine power take away from all over the world, this grievous pandemic of coronavirus. Inspire all authorities to take effective measures to contain the disease. Help us to be alert and vigilant against corona virus and to follow all guidelines and

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directions. You redeemed and saved us through the suffering and resurrection of Jesus. Help us not be discouraged but to believe and hope that you will bring good out of this evil. Father let your victory and glory shine through this deadly disease. Through Christ our Lord. Amen.”

Altruism in Caring for Sick

Probably during the times of pandemic, we would usually dread to come closer to any sick or aged person, and care for them. The natural tendency for self-preservation might overwhelm us. Of course, we are instructed to maintain social distance strictly with the COVID-19 contracted persons, but not with all the sick. However, if nobody else is present to nurse and care for the sick, we need to care for them prudently even if it were to be a COVID-19 victim, although it involves risks. Altruism urges us to do the needful within our capacity for the sick as Good Samaritan did in the parable (Lk. 10: 25-37).

Altruism in Accepting Simple Life-Style

Generally altruistic persons do not give gorgeous appearance of themselves and would not choose to feast while his/her neighbour is in distress or turmoil. They live a simple life. The coronavirus spread has made all of us not to go to malls, gyms, cinema theatres, stadium, tourist places, bars and restaurants. For those who are used to such places it would be hard. At this pandemic moment, altruism insists that we do not regret for lack of entertainments or get annoyed/bored for remaining at home. With regard to consumption, our life-style ought to exemplify sparingness which we (church leaders) preach to others, as necessary in order that so many millions of hungry people throughout the world may be fed⁴.

Conclusion

Although deadly and mysterious COVID-19 has brought tremendous havoc in terms of so many increasing numbers of

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death tolls and standstill of the global community, yet it provides an opportunity to investigate our altruistic attitude. If we just continue to do things selfishly, we would contribute for the greater destruction of the humanity. On the contrary, if we act with the sense of altruism and solidarity with humanity, we certainly save many lives. Hence, it is time for us to act as Jesus, our Good Shepherd, did “I came that they may have life, and have it abundantly” (Jn. 10:10). Altruism, if need to be, accepts sacrificing one’s own life but never jeopardizes other’s life. Altruism acts in consonance with selfless love of our neighbours. Our love of neighbour is to understood as nothing but our love of God itself. “Each of the manifold ways we are sacrificing to love our neighbours-- self-isolation, quarantining, tending to the sick at home, supporting first responders, avoiding public places, not hoarding supplies, working remotely and even not going physically to church buildings-- is itself an expression of our love of God⁵.” Thereby COVID-19 pandemic could be seen as an opportunity to strengthen our discipleship with Jesus: “By this (altruistic attitude and acts) everyone will know that you are my disciples, if you have love for one another” (Jn. 13:35).

¹ George V. Lobo, *Christian Living: According to Vatican II* (Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 1999), 293.

² David Gilbert, “Dropping Dead After Walking Hundreds of Miles During Coronavirus Lockdown”, accessed on 1st April 2020, https://www.vice.com/en_us/article/qjd5z5/people-in-india-are-dropping-dead-after-walking-hundreds-of-miles-during-coronavirus-lockdown.

³ Catherine Mowry LaCugna, *God for Us* (New York: Harper San Francisco, 1991), 397.

⁴ Synod of Bishops, *Justice in the World* (1971). # 48.

⁵ Daniel P. Horan, “For the Love of God (literally), Stay Home, and Be Safe and Pray” in *National Catholic Reporter* accessed on 2nd April 2020 <https://www.ncronline.org/news/opinion/faith-seeking-understanding/love-god-literally-stay-home-be-safe-and-pray?clickSource=email>.